

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE & MANAGEMENT

I
J
R
C
M

A Monthly Double-Blind Peer Reviewed (Refereed/Juried) Open Access International e-Journal - Included in the International Serial Directories

Indexed & Listed at:

Ulrich's Periodicals Directory ©, ProQuest, U.S.A., EBSCO Publishing, U.S.A., Cabell's Directories of Publishing Opportunities, U.S.A.

as well as in Open J-Gate, India (link of the same is duly available at Infibnet of University Grants Commission (U.G.C.))

Registered & Listed at: Index Copernicus Publishers Panel, Poland & number of libraries all around the world.

Circulated all over the world & Google has verified that scholars of more than 1667 Cities in 145 countries/territories are visiting our journal on regular basis.

Ground Floor, Building No. 1041-C-1, Devi Bhawan Bazar, JAGADHRI – 135 003, Yamunanagar, Haryana, INDIA

www.ijrcm.org.in

CONTENTS

Sr. No.	TITLE & NAME OF THE AUTHOR (S)	Page No.
1.	AN INQUIRY INTO THE PRODUCTIVITY OF INDIAN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY: APPLICATION OF DATA ENVELOPMENT ANALYSIS <i>UMANG GUPTA & ROHIT KAPOOR</i>	1
2.	GLOBALIZATION AND GROWTH OF INDIAN LIFE INSURANCE INDUSTRY <i>SUSHIL KUMAR, NIRAJ MISHRA & SEEMA VARSHNEY</i>	7
3.	ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL AND FACTORS INFLUENCING ADMITTED CUSTOMERS' SATISFACTION WITH HEALTH CARE SERVICE IN UNIVERSITY OF GONDAR TEACHING HOSPITAL, NORTH WEST ETHIOPIA <i>DIGISIE MEQUANINT & DR. ASSEGID DEMISIE</i>	10
4.	STOCK MARKET CRISIS AND VALUE RELEVANCE OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION: IMPACT ON QUOTED CEMENT MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN NIGERIA <i>SAMAILA THOMPSON & ABUH ADAH</i>	16
5.	SERVANT LEADERSHIP: A NEW PARADIGM OF LEADERSHIP IN BANGLADESH <i>MD. SAJJAD HOSSAIN & ULLAH S M EBRAHIM</i>	20
6.	PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE MOBILISATION IN ABURA-ASEBU-KWAMANKESE DISTRICT ASSEMBLY, GHANA <i>CHRISTOPHER DICK-SAGOE</i>	26
7.	AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONSTRAINTS FACED BY PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) IN INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UTTAR PRADESH <i>DR. ZEESHAN AMIR & ANIS UR REHMAN</i>	32
8.	PERFORMANCE OF INDIAN BANK WITH REFERENCE TO NON PERFORMING ASSETS – AN OVERVIEW <i>B. SELVARAJAN, DR. G. VADIVALAGAN & DR. M. CHANDRASEKAR</i>	38
9.	RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY AMONG PASSENGER CAR USERS (AN EMPIRICAL STUDY CONDUCTED IN BANGALORE CITY AMONG SMALL PASSENGER CAR USERS) <i>SRI.R.SRIVATS & DR. R. K. GOPAL</i>	47
10.	INFLUENCE OF QUALITY CIRCLES ON ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY <i>DR. D. S. CHAUBEY, RANI RAMASWAMY & NIDHI MAITHEL</i>	53
11.	PERFORMANCE OF TAX SAVING FUNDS OF SELECTED ASSET MANAGEMENT COMPANIES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS <i>DR. K. V. S. N. JAWAHAR BABU & DR. M.S. VASU</i>	60
12.	IMPACT OF MICRO - CREDIT TO WOMEN SHGS – A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO NAGAPATTINAM DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU <i>K. MUTHU. & DR. K. RAMAKRISHNAN.</i>	70
13.	MANAGERIAL EFFECTIVENESS AND COUNTERPRODUCTIVE WORK BEHAVIOUR: A COMPARISON AT DIFFERENT MANAGERIAL LEVEL <i>DR. RISHIPAL</i>	74
14.	A STUDY ON HEALTH INSURANCE PRODUCT PERFORMANCE AT HDFC, BANGALORE <i>V. CHANDRAMOHAN & DR. K. RAMACHANDRA</i>	79
15.	A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN BANKING SECTOR IN INDIA (INDUSTRIAL CREDIT AND INVESTMENT CORPORATION OF INDIA AND STATE BANK OF INDIA) <i>DR. PONDURI.S.B. & V. SAILAJA</i>	89
16.	WORK ETHICS AND ITS IMPACT ON JOB SATISFACTION OF INDIAN MANAGEMENT TEACHERS - AN EMPIRICAL STUDY <i>DR. RAJESHWARI NARENDRAN & PREETI MEHTA</i>	98
17.	AN APPRAISAL OF QUALITY OF SERVICES IN URBAN HOSPITALS (A STUDY ON THREE URBAN HOSPITALS IN GUNTUR DISTRICT, ANDHRA PRADESH) <i>DR. T. SREENIVAS & NETHI SURESH BABU</i>	103
18.	PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF SOME SELECT EQUITY FUNDS FLOATED BY PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS <i>B. RAJA MANNAR & DR. B. RAMACHANDRA REDDY</i>	113
19.	ANALYSING THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF IRON AND STEEL INDUSTRY WITH THE HELP OF MARKET VALUE ADDED APPROACH <i>E. LAVANYA & DR. B. RAMACHANDRA REDDY</i>	117
20.	ACHIEVING CUSTOMER LIFETIME VALUE THROUGH CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT <i>SHAKEEL-UL-REHMAN & DR. M. SELVARAJ</i>	120
21.	COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE OF BANKING COMPANIES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO STATE BANK OF INDIA AND ICICI BANK <i>DR. ANURAG B. SINGH & PRIYANKA TANDON</i>	124
22.	MANAGING BRAND EXTENSION <i>DR. C. MUTHUVELAYUTHAM & T. PRABHU.</i>	132
23.	BEHAVIOURAL ISSUES IN EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT <i>NISHI TRIPATHI & RICHA SINHA</i>	135
24.	STATUTORY DISCLOSURE BY INDIAN LIFE INSURANCE COMPANIES <i>GAGANDEEP KAUR & RAJINDER KAUR</i>	139
25.	PRODUCT LINE STRATEGY ADOPTED BY SMALL SCALE MOTOR AND PUMP INDUSTRY <i>DR. J. SUGANTHI</i>	144
26.	FACTORS OF CRM (A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BANKS) <i>DR. S. GAYATHRY</i>	149
27.	IMPACT OF GRIEVANCES AND REDRESSAL OF EMPLOYEES IN TEXTILE MILLS, COIMBATORE <i>P. DEEPA ANANDA PRIYA & DIVYA.S</i>	156
28.	A STUDY OF EMPLOYEE COMPETENCY MAPPING STRATEGIES AT SELECT ORGANISATIONS OF BANGALORE <i>DR. Y. NAGARAJU & V. SATHYANARAYANA GOWDA</i>	176
29.	COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ORGANIZATIONAL ROLE STRESS AMONG EMPLOYEES: PUBLIC VS PRIVATE BANKS IN INDIA <i>SHADMA PARVEEN</i>	182
30.	AN EMPIRICAL EXAMINATION OF NONWORK DOMAIN ON EMPLOYEE TURNOVER <i>L.R.K. KRISHNAN</i>	189
	REQUEST FOR FEEDBACK	201

CHIEF PATRON

PROF. K. K. AGGARWAL

Chancellor, Lingaya's University, Delhi
Founder Vice-Chancellor, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, Delhi
Ex. Pro Vice-Chancellor, Guru Jambheshwar University, Hisar

FOUNDER PATRON

LATE SH. RAM BHAJAN AGGARWAL

Former State Minister for Home & Tourism, Government of Haryana
Former Vice-President, Dadri Education Society, Charkhi Dadri
Former President, Chinar Syntex Ltd. (Textile Mills), Bhiwani

CO-ORDINATOR

DR. SAMBHAV GARG

Faculty, M. M. Institute of Management, MaharishiMarkandeshwarUniversity, Mullana, Ambala, Haryana

ADVISORS

DR. PRIYA RANJAN TRIVEDI

Chancellor, The Global Open University, Nagaland

PROF. M. S. SENAM RAJU

Director A. C. D., School of Management Studies, I.G.N.O.U., New Delhi

PROF. M. N. SHARMA

Chairman, M.B.A., HaryanaCollege of Technology & Management, Kaithal

PROF. S. L. MAHANDRU

Principal (Retd.), MaharajaAgrasenCollege, Jagadhri

EDITOR

PROF. R. K. SHARMA

Professor, Bharti Vidyapeeth University Institute of Management & Research, New Delhi

CO-EDITOR

DR. BHAVET

Faculty, M. M. Institute of Management, MaharishiMarkandeshwarUniversity, Mullana, Ambala, Haryana

EDITORIAL ADVISORY BOARD

DR. RAJESH MODI

Faculty, YanbuIndustrialCollege, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

PROF. SANJIV MITTAL

UniversitySchool of Management Studies, Guru Gobind Singh I. P. University, Delhi

PROF. ANIL K. SAINI

Chairperson (CRC), Guru Gobind Singh I. P. University, Delhi

DR. SAMBHAVNA

Faculty, I.I.T.M., Delhi

DR. MOHENDER KUMAR GUPTA

Associate Professor, P.J.L.N.Government College, Faridabad

DR. SHIVAKUMAR DEENE

Asst. Professor, Dept. of Commerce, School of Business Studies, Central University of Karnataka, Gulbarga

DR. MOHITA

Faculty, Yamuna Institute of Engineering & Technology, Village Gadholi, P. O. Gadholi, Yamunanagar

ASSOCIATE EDITORS

PROF. NAWAB ALI KHAN

Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, U.P.

PROF. ABHAY BANSAL

Head, Department of Information Technology, Amity School of Engineering & Technology, Amity University, Noida

PROF. V. SELVAM

SSL, VIT University, Vellore

PROF. N. SUNDARAM

VIT University, Vellore

DR. PARDEEP AHLAWAT

Associate Professor, Institute of Management Studies & Research, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak

DR. S. TABASSUM SULTANA

Associate Professor, Department of Business Management, Matrusri Institute of P.G. Studies, Hyderabad

TECHNICAL ADVISOR

AMITA

Faculty, Government M. S., Mohali

DR. MOHITA

Faculty, Yamuna Institute of Engineering & Technology, Village Gadholi, P. O. Gadholi, Yamunanagar

FINANCIAL ADVISORS

DICKIN GOYAL

Advocate & Tax Adviser, Panchkula

NEENA

Investment Consultant, Chambaghat, Solan, Himachal Pradesh

LEGAL ADVISORS

JITENDER S. CHAHAL

Advocate, Punjab & Haryana High Court, Chandigarh U.T.

CHANDER BHUSHAN SHARMA

Advocate & Consultant, District Courts, Yamunanagar at Jagadhri

SUPERINTENDENT

SURENDER KUMAR POONIA

CALL FOR MANUSCRIPTS

We invite unpublished novel, original, empirical and high quality research work pertaining to recent developments & practices in the area of Computer, Business, Finance, Marketing, Human Resource Management, General Management, Banking, Insurance, Corporate Governance and emerging paradigms in allied subjects like Accounting Education; Accounting Information Systems; Accounting Theory & Practice; Auditing; Behavioral Accounting; Behavioral Economics; Corporate Finance; Cost Accounting; Econometrics; Economic Development; Economic History; Financial Institutions & Markets; Financial Services; Fiscal Policy; Government & Non Profit Accounting; Industrial Organization; International Economics & Trade; International Finance; Macro Economics; Micro Economics; Monetary Policy; Portfolio & Security Analysis; Public Policy Economics; Real Estate; Regional Economics; Tax Accounting; Advertising & Promotion Management; Business Education; Management Information Systems (MIS); Business Law, Public Responsibility & Ethics; Communication; Direct Marketing; E-Commerce; Global Business; Health Care Administration; Labor Relations & Human Resource Management; Marketing Research; Marketing Theory & Applications; Non-Profit Organizations; Office Administration/Management; Operations Research/Statistics; Organizational Behavior & Theory; Organizational Development; Production/Operations; Public Administration; Purchasing/Materials Management; Retailing; Sales/Selling; Services; Small Business Entrepreneurship; Strategic Management Policy; Technology/Innovation; Tourism, Hospitality & Leisure; Transportation/Physical Distribution; Algorithms; Artificial Intelligence; Compilers & Translation; Computer Aided Design (CAD); Computer Aided Manufacturing; Computer Graphics; Computer Organization & Architecture; Database Structures & Systems; Digital Logic; Discrete Structures; Internet; Management Information Systems; Modeling & Simulation; Multimedia; Neural Systems/Neural Networks; Numerical Analysis/Scientific Computing; Object Oriented Programming; Operating Systems; Programming Languages; Robotics; Symbolic & Formal Logic and Web Design. The above mentioned tracks are only indicative, and not exhaustive.

Anybody can submit the soft copy of his/her manuscript **anytime** in M.S. Word format after preparing the same as per our submission guidelines duly available on our website under the heading guidelines for submission, at the email address: infoijrcm@gmail.com.

GUIDELINES FOR SUBMISSION OF MANUSCRIPT

1. **COVERING LETTER FOR SUBMISSION:**

DATED: _____

THE EDITOR
IJRCM

Subject: SUBMISSION OF MANUSCRIPT IN THE AREA OF

(e.g. Finance/Marketing/HRM/General Management/Economics/Psychology/Law/Computer/IT/Engineering/Mathematics/other, please specify)

DEAR SIR/MADAM

Please find my submission of manuscript entitled ' _____ ' for possible publication in your journals.

I hereby affirm that the contents of this manuscript are original. Furthermore, it has neither been published elsewhere in any language fully or partly, nor is it under review for publication elsewhere.

I affirm that all the author (s) have seen and agreed to the submitted version of the manuscript and their inclusion of name (s) as co-author (s).

Also, if my/our manuscript is accepted, I/We agree to comply with the formalities as given on the website of the journal & you are free to publish our contribution in any of your journals.

NAME OF CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

Designation:

Affiliation with full address, contact numbers & Pin Code:

Residential address with Pin Code:

Mobile Number (s):

Landline Number (s):

E-mail Address:

Alternate E-mail Address:

NOTES:

- a) The whole manuscript is required to be in **ONE MS WORD FILE** only (pdf. version is liable to be rejected without any consideration), which will start from the covering letter, inside the manuscript.
- b) The sender is required to mention the following in the **SUBJECT COLUMN** of the mail:
New Manuscript for Review in the area of (Finance/Marketing/HRM/General Management/Economics/Psychology/Law/Computer/IT/Engineering/Mathematics/other, please specify)
- c) There is no need to give any text in the body of mail, except the cases where the author wishes to give any specific message w.r.t. to the manuscript.
- d) The total size of the file containing the manuscript is required to be below **500 KB**.
- e) Abstract alone will not be considered for review, and the author is required to submit the complete manuscript in the first instance.
- f) The journal gives acknowledgement w.r.t. the receipt of every email and in case of non-receipt of acknowledgment from the journal, w.r.t. the submission of manuscript, within two days of submission, the corresponding author is required to demand for the same by sending separate mail to the journal.

2. **MANUSCRIPT TITLE:** The title of the paper should be in a 12 point Calibri Font. It should be bold typed, centered and fully capitalised.

3. **AUTHOR NAME (S) & AFFILIATIONS:** The author (s) **full name, designation, affiliation (s), address, mobile/landline numbers, and email/alternate email address** should be in italic & 11-point Calibri Font. It must be centered underneath the title.

4. **ABSTRACT:** Abstract should be in fully italicized text, not exceeding 250 words. The abstract must be informative and explain the background, aims, methods, results & conclusion in a single para. Abbreviations must be mentioned in full.

5. **KEYWORDS:** Abstract must be followed by a list of keywords, subject to the maximum of five. These should be arranged in alphabetic order separated by commas and full stops at the end.
6. **MANUSCRIPT:** Manuscript must be in **BRITISH ENGLISH** prepared on a standard A4 size **PORTRAIT SETTING PAPER**. It must be prepared on a single space and single column with 1" margin set for top, bottom, left and right. It should be typed in 8 point Calibri Font with page numbers at the bottom and centre of every page. It should be free from grammatical, spelling and punctuation errors and must be thoroughly edited.
7. **HEADINGS:** All the headings should be in a 10 point Calibri Font. These must be bold-faced, aligned left and fully capitalised. Leave a blank line before each heading.
8. **SUB-HEADINGS:** All the sub-headings should be in a 8 point Calibri Font. These must be bold-faced, aligned left and fully capitalised.
9. **MAIN TEXT:** The main text should follow the following sequence:

INTRODUCTION**REVIEW OF LITERATURE****NEED/IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY****STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM****OBJECTIVES****HYPOTHESES****RESEARCH METHODOLOGY****RESULTS & DISCUSSION****FINDINGS****RECOMMENDATIONS/SUGGESTIONS****CONCLUSIONS****SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH****ACKNOWLEDGMENTS****REFERENCES****APPENDIX/ANNEXURE**

It should be in a 8 point Calibri Font, single spaced and justified. The manuscript should preferably not exceed **5000 WORDS**.

10. **FIGURES & TABLES:** These should be simple, crystal clear, centered, separately numbered & self explained, and **titles must be above the table/figure. Sources of data should be mentioned below the table/figure.** It should be ensured that the tables/figures are referred to from the main text.
11. **EQUATIONS:** These should be consecutively numbered in parentheses, horizontally centered with equation number placed at the right.
12. **REFERENCES:** The list of all references should be alphabetically arranged. The author (s) should mention only the actually utilised references in the preparation of manuscript and they are supposed to follow **Harvard Style of Referencing**. The author (s) are supposed to follow the references as per the following:
 - All works cited in the text (including sources for tables and figures) should be listed alphabetically.
 - Use (ed.) for one editor, and (ed.s) for multiple editors.
 - When listing two or more works by one author, use --- (20xx), such as after Kohl (1997), use --- (2001), etc, in chronologically ascending order.
 - Indicate (opening and closing) page numbers for articles in journals and for chapters in books.
 - The title of books and journals should be in italics. Double quotation marks are used for titles of journal articles, book chapters, dissertations, reports, working papers, unpublished material, etc.
 - For titles in a language other than English, provide an English translation in parentheses.
 - The location of endnotes within the text should be indicated by superscript numbers.

PLEASE USE THE FOLLOWING FOR STYLE AND PUNCTUATION IN REFERENCES:**BOOKS**

- Bowersox, Donald J., Closs, David J., (1996), "Logistical Management." Tata McGraw, Hill, New Delhi.
- Hunker, H.L. and A.J. Wright (1963), "Factors of Industrial Location in Ohio" Ohio State University, Nigeria.

CONTRIBUTIONS TO BOOKS

- Sharma T., Kwatra, G. (2008) Effectiveness of Social Advertising: A Study of Selected Campaigns, Corporate Social Responsibility, Edited by David Crowther & Nicholas Capaldi, Ashgate Research Companion to Corporate Social Responsibility, Chapter 15, pp 287-303.

JOURNAL AND OTHER ARTICLES

- Schemenner, R.W., Huber, J.C. and Cook, R.L. (1987), "Geographic Differences and the Location of New Manufacturing Facilities," Journal of Urban Economics, Vol. 21, No. 1, pp. 83-104.

CONFERENCE PAPERS

- Garg, Sambhav (2011): "Business Ethics" Paper presented at the Annual International Conference for the All India Management Association, New Delhi, India, 19-22 June.

UNPUBLISHED DISSERTATIONS AND THESES

- Kumar S. (2011): "Customer Value: A Comparative Study of Rural and Urban Customers," Thesis, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.

ONLINE RESOURCES

- Always indicate the date that the source was accessed, as online resources are frequently updated or removed.

WEBSITES

- Garg, Bhavet (2011): Towards a New Natural Gas Policy, Political Weekly, Viewed on January 01, 2012 <http://epw.in/user/viewabstract.jsp>

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF SOME SELECT EQUITY FUNDS FLOATED BY PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS

B. RAJA MANNAR
RESEARCH SCHOLAR
DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE
SRI VENKATESWARA UNIVERSITY
TIRUPATI

DR. B. RAMACHANDRA REDDY
PROFESSOR
DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE
SRI VENKATESWARA UNIVERSITY
TIRUPATI

ABSTRACT

The mutual funds from the private sector banks, HDFC and ICICI, two each from each group, Top 200 Growth, Capital Builder, Top 200 and Top 100 schemes of Growth Option are selected for evaluation in the present context. Long standing and steady growth formed the basis of the selection. These funds are statistically evaluated by standard deviation, correlation with market index, and the financial parameters, Sharpe's Index, Treynor Index, Jensen's alpha, Fama's Measure and M^2 . The results indicate the supremacy of HDFC Top 200 fund over the others.

KEYWORDS

Evaluation of mutual funds of the Private Sector Banks, HDFC and ICICI Prudential, Statistical appraisal of Top 200, capital Builder, Top 200 and Top 100 growth schemes.

INTRODUCTION

Mutual fund is defined as "a fund in the form of a trust by a sponsor, to rise money by the trustees through the sale of units to the public for investing in securities under the framework of the regulations". The Indian Mutual Fund Industry emerged as a dominant financial intermediary in Indian capital market during the last couple of years. Small investors can take benefits of stock market growth by investing in equity and debt instruments through MF. The appreciation of investment depends on the performance of fund and stock market. A mutual fund benefits from professional fund managers who can apply their expertise and dedicate time to research investment options. Thus funds play a significant role in financial intermediation development of capital markets and growth of the financial sector as a whole.

Performance evaluation of mutual funds is built on the twin expectations of the investors namely, risk premium and scheme's return over the market return. A preview of the performance of a mutual fund can serve as a guideline and to an extent in the selection of a fund for investment. However, past performance may not be a true representative of the future trend, and a cautious approach may be required.

A study of the available literature indicates that not all of the possible available tools are applied for the evaluation of mutual funds. Some of the research can be seen focused only on particular fund and highlights the advantage and disadvantages of that fund.

The most appropriate and commonly applied tool for assessing the performance of mutual fund scheme is to track the NAV. Future performance is predictable from past performance as funds are bought and sold based on NAV of schemes. Equity schemes are the close substitute for direct investment in capital market. As equity based schemes are comparatively riskier; investors expect return in relation to the risk involved. Hence, a better way to assess the portfolio is to consider return per unit of risk. To measure the risk, two appropriate quantitative risk surrogates that can be used are: standard deviation of rate of return and beta coefficient of the portfolio. Markowitz's portfolio theory paved the way for a new direction to the risk-return analysis of portfolios. The CAPM developed by Sharpe (1964) and John Lintner (1969) laid the foundation stone for the growth of capital market. Treynor (1965) and Jensen (1968) made remarkable contribution by developing models to evaluate portfolios. Fama made a valuable contribution to decompose return into various components. An empirical review of NAV of the selected growth schemes bequeaths a better understanding of the mutual fund schemes performance.

The present work is designed to evaluate the performance of the four equity funds selected, two each from the fund houses, HDFC and ICICI Prudential. The funds selected are HDFC Top 200 (G), HDFC Capital Builder (G), ICICI Prudential Top 200 (G) and ICICI Prudential Top 100 (G). As it is aimed at an exhaustive study of these funds, the period envisaged the past ten years, starting from the financial year 2002 - 03 to the end of the financial year 2011-12.

The sole idea behind selecting these funds being:

It is needless to mention that these funds have a long track record and withstood the acid test of time during various intervals.

DATA COMPILATION AND COMPUTATION OF STATISTICAL EVALUATION PARAMETERS

The Equity funds selected for appraisal include:

1. HDFC Top 200 Growth: Designed to generate long term capital appreciation by investing in a portfolio of equities and equity linked instruments drawn from the BSE 200 Index.
2. HDFC Capital Builder Growth: The Investment Objective of the Scheme is to achieve capital appreciation in the long term.
3. ICICI Prudential Top 200 Growth: Aims to generate capital appreciation through investments in equity related securities in core sectors and associated feeder industries
4. ICICI Prudential Top 100 Growth: Seeks to generate capital appreciation by actively investing in equity and equity related securities. For defensive considerations, the Scheme may invest in debt, money market instruments and derivatives

TABLE 1: FUND INFORMATION

Information	HDFC		ICICI	
	Top 200	Capital Builder	Top 200	Top 100
Type of scheme	Open Ended	Open Ended	Open Ended	Open Ended
Nature of scheme	Equity+	Growth Scheme	Equity	
Launch date	Sep 11, 1996	January, 1994	Oct 1, 1994	Jun 19, 1998
Face value Rs. /Unit	10		10	10
Fund size (Rs. cr.)	11,381.06 (31/03/12)	41,333.28 (31/03/12)	477.00 (31/03/12)	304.93 (31/03/12)
Minimum investment (Rs.)	5000	5000	5000	5000
Purchase redemptions	Daily	Every Business Day	Daily	Daily
NAV Calculations	Daily	Every Business Day.	Daily	Daily
NAV (Rs./Unit) as on 31-03-2012	185.967	106.6710	97.79	138.93
Entry load	0%.	Nil	0%.	NA
Exit load	1% If redeemed between 0 to 1 Year.	1% If redeemed within 1 year. No Exit Load if redeemed after 1 year	1% if redeemed between 0 to 1 Year;	1% if redeemed/ switched out within a period of 15 months.

FIG. 1: COMPARISON OF THE SELECTED FUNDS

The NAV values of the selected schemes were drawn for the period of study from the respective web sites of the fund managers. The monthly returns were obtained as

$$R_{PN} = \left(\frac{NAV_{Closing} - NAV_{Opening}}{NAV_{Opening}} \right) + 1 \quad (1)$$

The R_{PN} for a financial year are compounded for the annualized return, R_p .

$$R_p = \left(GM_{RP_1, RP_2, \dots, RP_{12}} \right) - 1 \quad (2)$$

Where GM is the geometric mean.

Comparison of the performance of a fund with the market or index performance indicates as to how well or worse the managed portfolio performed vis-a-vis market return vis-à-vis market return. Monthly values of S&P NSE Nifty were drawn from www.nseindia.com for the study period, financial year 2002 to 2012 to compute the market return (R_m) with reference to the funds.

The other parameter required for obtaining the evaluation parameters is the risk free return, R_f . Risk free rate of return is the available rate of return from investing in a risk free asset. The asset with the known terminal value is risk free asset. Government securities and deposits in national Banks fall under this category. Interest rate earned on the savings bank deposit of State bank of India is selected as the risk free rate in the present study.

The rate of return offered by SBI on savings bank deposit is 4% for the financial year 2011-12 and 2002-03 and for the financial years 2003-04 through 2010 it is 3.5% per annum. Average risk free monthly returns are 0.330% and 0.292% respectively.

The selected mutual funds are statistically evaluated for the study period, employing the average values obtained over the study period of Sharpe's Index (S_i), Treynor's Index (T_i), Jensen's Alpha (α_i), Fama's Measure and M^2 .

The models developed on the assumptions of 'The Capital Asset Pricing Model' and tested by Treynor (1965), Sharpe (1966), Jensen (1968) and Fama's Decomposition of Returns was used to evaluate the performance of selected growth schemes. M^2 was employed for the intercorrelation of the evaluation parameters.

Sharpe Index (S_i) : measures the risk premium of the portfolio with reference to the total amount of risk. The index S_i measures the slope of the line emanating from risk-free rate outward the portfolio. The larger the S_i , the better the portfolio has performed. S_i is the reward to variability of the scheme's total risk and is a summary measure of scheme's performance adjusted for risk.

$$S_i = \frac{A_{pt} - R_f}{\sigma_{pt}} \quad (3)$$

Where

S_i = Sharpe Index

R_f = Risk-free rate of return

A_{pt} = Average return on portfolio 't'

σ_{pt} = Risk involved in portfolio 't' returns

Treynor Index (T_i) sums up the risk and return of a portfolio in a single number. The index measures the slope of the line emanating outward from the risk-free rate to the portfolio under consideration. Treynor index is a reward to volatility of the portfolio. The characteristic line relates the market return to a specific portfolio return without any direct adjustment for risk. This line can be fitted through a least square regression involving a single market portfolio.

$$T_i = \frac{AR_p - R_f}{\beta_p} \quad (4)$$

Jensen constructed a measure of absolute performance on a risk-adjusted basis while Sharpe and Treynor models provided measures for ranking the relative performance of various portfolios on a risk-adjusted basis. Equilibrium average return on a portfolio is the benchmark. Equilibrium average return is the return of the market portfolio for a given systematic risk being :

$$EAR_p = R_f + (R_m - R_f) \beta \quad (5)$$

EAR_p is the equilibrium return of the portfolio 'p' indicating superior / inferior performance of the portfolio's alpha (α_i). Jensen's Alpha is the intercept of the CRL. If alpha is positive, the portfolio has performed better and if it is negative, scheme performance is not up to the benchmark. In a well-diversified portfolio, the average value of alpha of all stocks turns out to be zero.

Eugene Fama's Decomposition of Total Returns: Eugene Fama provides for an analytical framework, which enables for a detailed analysis of scheme performance popularly known as Fama's Decomposition of Total Return. The total return on a portfolio constitutes of risk-free return (R_f) and excess return.

The excess return arises from different factors such as risk accepted and stock selection. The excess return can be decomposed into two components, namely risk premium (reward for bearing risk) and for stock selectivity (return from stock selection).

Each portfolio will have both systematic risk and unsystematic risk. Hence risk premium can be decomposed into two components namely, return for bearing systematic risk (market risk) and return for bearing unsystematic risk.

The return for pure (net) selectivity is the additional return obtained by a portfolio manager for his superior stock selection ability over and above the return mandated by the total risk of the portfolio.

Fama's net selectivity (F_p) is

$$F_p = R_p - \left[R_f + \frac{\sigma_p}{\sigma_M} (R_M - R_f) \right] \quad (6)$$

M^2 : The relative measures of performance, the Sharpe or Treynor Index are simple and primarily used to rank the funds. The numerical values of these parameters are not easy to interpret. Modigliani proposed a variant of Sharpe Index named M^2 Measure. Unlike Sharpe Index, M^2 is an absolute measure of return. Like Sharpe Index, this measure uses total volatility as a measure of risk and reflects the proposition that by choosing a portfolio for investing matters in measuring its performance, is total risk, and not just systematic risk. However, its risk adjusted measure of performance has the easy interpretation of a differential return relative to the benchmark index. Performance can be simply be measured by comparing the returns from the market index and that of adjusted portfolio. This performance measure is defined as

$$M^2 = \left[\frac{\sigma_M(R_p) + 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_M(R_p)}{\sigma_r} \right) \right] - R_M \quad (7)$$

The M^2 is the difference between the two returns. When the capital Allocation Line (CAL) of the portfolio is less steep than CML, M^2 would be negative, signifying below normal performance of the fund manager. When the CAL is steeper than CML, M^2 will be positive, signifying above normal performance of the fund manager.

LIMITATIONS

- Investments decisions taken based on statistical data might not yield desired returns.
- All the caveats attached to mutual funds will apply to the funds selected for this study.
- Banks are free to accept deposits at any interest rates within the ceiling fixed by Reserve Bank of India. Hence there can be possibility in the accuracy of risk free rates.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The R_p of the selected funds, corresponding R_m values and their σ values are included in Table.2 and are represented by Fig.1, for comparison and correlation. Standard deviation represents the risk involved in the mutual fund and hence the fund with a low standard deviation is favored. The standard deviation data indicates that the average performance being far more inferior of the HDFC top 200 scheme by a large factor compared to the other schemes under study. The performance of all the funds were to an extent better than the market with only a few rare exceptions. This observation is based on the comparison of R_m and R_p values correlation between the fund and the market was reasonable in the case of HDFC Top 200 and ICICI Prudential Top 100 schemes where as the other two schemes are par below performance wise compared to the market.

TABLE.2. PORTFOLIO RETURN (R_p), MARKET RETURN (R_M), CORRELATION COEFFICIENT $Corr_{(R_p, R_M)}$ AND STANDARD DEVIATION (Σ) OF THE SCHEMES

YEAR \ FUND	HDFC		ICICI Prudential		S&P CNX Nifty
	Top 200(G)	Capital Builder(G)	Top 200(G)	Top 100(G)	
	R_p				R_M
2011-12	-0.0051	0.0013	0.0364	-0.0050	-0.0120
2010-11	1.0073	-0.1050	0.0020	0.0014	0.0058
2009-10	5.2871	0.0154	-0.0040	0.0195	0.0047
2008-09	-3.6507	-0.0378	-0.0033	-0.0018	-0.0383
2007-08	2.3347	0.0227	0.0157	0.0063	0.0179
2006-07	0.0445	-0.001	-0.0777	0.0012	0.0100
2005-06	4.6386	-0.0233	0.0338	0.0387	0.0439
2004-05	1.4034	0.0122	0.0124	0.0034	0.0116
2003-04	1.1194	0.0511	0.0125	0.0713	0.0512
2002-03	-1.022	-0.001	-0.019	-0.008	-0.011
Σ	2.6052	0.04227	0.03239	0.02471	0.02622
$Corr_{(R_p, R_M)}$	0.8588	0.4102	0.1612	0.8271	

The results of the statistical evaluation parameters are presented in Table.3. Sharpe Rule stipulates that in assessing the comparative merits of the funds a fund with higher S_h is to be chosen. An investor with a different risk performance might choose a different base. Higher the Sharpe Ratio, more attractive the fund becomes. In the present study, it can be seen that HDFC Top 200 is the best performer of the selected lot. Others can be termed far most inferior due the negative values. High Treynor Ratio indicates a more attractive fund. The same order of merit of the schemes can be observed from the Treynor's Ratio comparison.

TABLE 3: STATISTICAL EVALUATION PARAMETERS OF THE SELECTED SCHEMES

Fund \ Perametar	HDFC		ICICI Prudential	ICICI Prudential
	Top 200(G)	Capital Builder(G)	Top 200(G)	Top 100(G)
S_t	2.92	-3.37	-2.72	-3.59
T_f	0.3682	-1.2697	-0.5779	-0.3739
α_j	0.3657	-0.1956	-0.4917	-0.5234
F_p	0.3639	0.7607	0.3276	0.3703
M^2	2.9351	0.5469	0.9130	0.2995

Only HDFC Top 200 has positive alpha. The inferences are that the other funds with negative alpha have underperformed the bench mark index. A high Fama's Information Ratio indicates a manager's ability to achieve higher returns. The F_p values are suggestive that the HDFC Capital Builder is healthier than the others; the other three schemes are of the same order. M^2 is positive, for all the schemes, signifying above normal performance of the fund manager. Spearman Rank Correlation (Table.4) of the Evaluation parameters was excellent between the evaluation parameters except the HDFC Top 200 Growth fund as expected as the fund's performance was different being far better than the other funds.

TABLE 4: SPEARMAN RANK CORRELATION OF THE EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Fund \ Perametar	HDFC		ICICI Prudential	ICICI Prudential
	Top 200(G)	Capital Builder(G)	Top 200(G)	Top 100(G)
S_t	1			
T_f	-0.379	1		
α_j	-0.257	0.960*	1	
F_p	-0.491	0.909	0.966*	1
M^2	-0.401	0.948*	0.921*	0.854*

* Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

In a nutshell, it can be concluded that HFC Top 200 followed by HDFC Capital Builder can become a best bet for the investors based on the past performance.

REFERENCES

- Daniel K.(1997), "Measuring Mutual Fund Performance with Characteristics based Benchmarks" The Journal of finance, Vol-II, No.3,pp.1035-1058.
- Genesan S.J. (2000), "Mutual Funds, Indian Management", Vol. 39, No. 10, p. p. 42.
- Gupta Amitabh.(2001), " Mutual Funds in India, A study of Investment Management", Finance India, Vol. 15, No. 2, pp. 631.
- Jain PK, (1982), "Financial Institution in India –A Study of Unit Trust of India", Triveri Publication, New Delhi.
- Jutur Sharath. (2004), "Evaluating Indian Mutual Funds", Chartered Financial Analyst, Vol. 10, pp. 83.
- Nimalathasan.B; R.Kumar Gandhi, (2012) Mutual Fund Financial Performance Analysis- A Comparative Study On Equity Diversified Schemes And Equity Mid-Cap Schemes., EXCEL International Journal of Multidisciplinary Management Studies Vol.2 Issue 3, March 2012, ISSN 2249 8834
- Nooney Lenin Kumar, Vangapandu Rama Devi, (2011) Performance Evaluation Of Private And Public Sponsored Mutual Funds In India. International Journal Of Research In Commerce, It & Management Volume No: 1 , Issue No. 2
- Sadhak, H., 1991, "The alternate saving media", The Economic Times, April 30, 9.
- SEBI – NCAER, 2000, Survey of Indian Investors, SEBI, Mumbai.
- Shiv Kumar Singh; Kriti Bhaswar Singh;. Abhisekh Singh, (2012), "Asian Journal Of Research In Banking And Finance , Vol.2. pp.51-61

WEBSITES

- www.amfiindia.com
- www.hdfcfund.com
- www.icicipruamc.com
- www.investsmartindia.com

REQUEST FOR FEEDBACK

Dear Readers

At the very outset, International Journal of Research in Commerce and Management (IJRCM) acknowledges & appreciates your efforts in showing interest in our present issue under your kind perusal.

I would like to request you to supply your critical comments and suggestions about the material published in this issue as well as on the journal as a whole, on our E-mail i.e. infoijrcm@gmail.com for further improvements in the interest of research.

If you have any queries please feel free to contact us on our E-mail infoijrcm@gmail.com.

I am sure that your feedback and deliberations would make future issues better – a result of our joint effort.

Looking forward an appropriate consideration.

With sincere regards

Thanking you profoundly

Academically yours

Sd/-

Co-ordinator

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

In this age of Commerce, Economics, Computer, I.T. & Management and cut throat competition, a group of intellectuals felt the need to have some platform, where young and budding managers and academicians could express their views and discuss the problems among their peers. This journal was conceived with this noble intention in view. This journal has been introduced to give an opportunity for expressing refined and innovative ideas in this field. It is our humble endeavour to provide a springboard to the upcoming specialists and give a chance to know about the latest in the sphere of research and knowledge. We have taken a small step and we hope that with the active co-operation of like-minded scholars, we shall be able to serve the society with our humble efforts.

Our Other Journals

